

SYNERGETIC REMEDIATION OF HCH-POLLUTED SEDIMENTS BY THE ALKALINE AND ULTRASONIC ACTIVATION OF PERSULFATE: PERFORMANCE AND RESIDUAL TOXICITY

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Lindane (γ -hexachlorocyclohexane, γ -HCH) has been commonly used as an insecticide in the last decades. This isomer was the only HCH with insecticidal properties, whereas the other HCH isomers (80-90% of the production) were uncontrolled disposed in unmanaged landfills [1]. An example of this large-scale HCH waste hot spot is the Bailín landfill (Sabiñánigo, Spain). Due to the global dimension of HCHs contamination, enormous research effort has been made to remediate this site. Several chemical oxidation technologies, such as Fenton process ($\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{Fe}$) and different persulfate (PS) activation methods (thermal, alkaline, and simultaneous application of temperature and alkali) have been tested for the remediation of these sediments, polluted with α -HCH and β -HCH [2]. Among them, the last one (PS/NaOH/T(40°C)) has resulted in promising results, achieving a pollutants conversion of 95% in 14 days of treatment. To reduce the reaction time, the process can be intensified by the application of other energy sources such as ultrasound (US) energy, increasing the generation of sulfate radicals ($\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$) by the following equation:

where “US” denotes ultrasonic irradiation. Moreover, US can enhance the desorption of the contaminants from the soil to the aqueous phase, improving the pollutant degradation efficiency [3]. Thus, it is expected that the combined application of PS/NaOH and US improves the results previously obtained, reducing the reaction time required without compromising the contaminant removal.

Real polluted sediments from the Bailín’s landfill (α -HCH = 282 mg kg⁻¹ and β -HCH = 110 mg kg⁻¹) have been treated to evaluate the intensification of the alkaline activation of PS with US. Batch experiments (liquid/soil ratio = 2) have been performed (PTFE reactors) at different US amplitudes (0, 25, 50 and 75%, corresponding with 0, 63, 162 and 245 W, respectively) using a Branson Digital Sonifier SFX 550 ($f = 20\text{kHz}$). The application of US leads to a gradual temperature increases in the reaction medium (from 22 °C to 50 °C, 67 °C and 75 °C when working with 25, 50 and 75% of amplitude, respectively, at 3h of reaction time), which highly enhances the efficiency of the process. To discriminate the US effect, additional tests have been conducted by applying the ramp temperature without US. Moreover, the effect of the initial PS concentration (10, 20, 40, and 60 g L⁻¹) has been studied. Pollutant (α -HCH and β -HCH) abatement, dechlorination degree (Cl^-/Cl_0), and oxidant consumption have been evaluated at the different operating conditions tested. Once selected the operating conditions, the ecotoxicity of the soil was measured by using the Microtox[®] bioassay to determine the toxicity reduction after the application of the remediation process.

The alkaline activation of PS (pH>12) causes in a first step the dehydrochlorination of HCHs to trichlorobenzenes (TCBs) [2], being the hydrolysis of the β -HCH isomer the limiting step ($X_{\alpha\text{-HCH}}=100\%$ at 4h). In this way, to evaluate the chlorinated organic compounds (COCs) conversion, the sum of HCHs and TCBs has been considered, and the fraction of TCBs generated and not oxidized (TCBs/HCH₀) has been determined. The consumption of PS is the result of i) COCs oxidation and ii) unproductive consumption of the oxidant. Therefore, to analyse the effect of the US application on PS decomposition, the results obtained in the presence of soil contaminated with COCs (named polluted

soil) have been compared with those obtained using clean soil (named unpolluted soil, this soil was collected from the same location and with the same physicochemical characteristics). The increase in PS consumption with US (*vs* no US) with the unpolluted soil is lower than with the polluted soil (Fig. 1-a). Since both soils differ in the presence of COCs, this fact could be attributable to a higher COCs oxidation rate against the unproductive PS consumption rate in this case. COCs conversion was significantly enhanced with increasing the US amplitude up to 50% (Fig. 1-b). US values above this value lead to a worse degradation of COCs (aspect previously reported in the literature [4]) although a higher dechlorination degree was achieved at these conditions.

Figure 1. Effect of US and T^a in (a) PS consumption (equivalent T^a ramp has been applied in the runs without US application) and in (b) fraction of TCBS generated, COCs degradation and dechlorination degree (liquid/soil = 2, PS = 40 gL⁻¹, NaOH:PS = 2 (pH>12), t = 3h).

On the other hand, COCs degradation and dechlorination improved by increasing the initial PS concentration (working with 50% of US), whereas the unproductive consumption of PS remained constant at the different initial PS concentrations, following a first-order reaction (data not shown). Thus, X_{PS} is mainly consumed in the oxidation of the pollutants. Based on the results obtained, 60 g L⁻¹ has been selected as the optimal PS concentration. Moreover, the low X_{PS} reached at these conditions (\approx 20%) allows the reuse of the supernatant to treat a new batch of polluted soil.

Ecotoxicity measurements of the soil before and after the chemical oxidation process proposed (NaOH:PS=2, PS = 60 g L⁻¹, US amplitude 50% (162W)) by the Microtox[®] bioassay demonstrated a significant decrease in the toxicity of the treated soil. Moreover, the initial TOC concentration was practically unaffected after the remediation process (it should be considered that COCs in the polluted soil represent 0.6% of TOC), highlighting that the initial soil characteristics remain unaltered.

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